

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF THE DEPENDENCE OF SANOGENIC THINKING ON PERSONALITY CHARACTERISTICS AND BEHAVIORAL STRUCTURE

Abdurakhmanova Zukhra

assistant professor of the Department of
Psychology, Tashkent University, (PhD)
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11409648>

ARTICLE INFO

Qabul qilindi: 20-May 2024 yil
Ma'qullandi: 25-May 2024 yil
Nashr qilindi: 31-May 2024 yil

KEY WORDS

*person, teenager, student youth,
pedagogue, parent, education,
upbringing, thinking, sanogenic
thinking.*

ABSTRACT

*factor analysis indicators of the results obtained from
questionnaires such as the study of factors of
personality characteristics taken from young students
are presented.*

The analysis of socio-psychological characteristics of the development of sanogenic thinking in early adolescents and their individual-psychological aspects is considered one of the necessary issues to research thinking and the place of sanogenic thinking in the system of public education institutions in our republic today. In order to psychologically more fully illuminate sanogenic thinking in early adolescents, their individual-psychological capabilities, the ability to easily perform complex activities that occur within the framework of educational activities, the correct establishment of interpersonal relationships with teachers, the high level of emotional intelligence in communication with the people around them, and the socio-psychological factors in determining the relationship between mutual psychological aspects, there are several questionnaires that determine the emergence of psychological factors that develop students' sanogenic thinking, i.e. the "Level of Anxiety" method developed by Spielberger Khanin, Ehlers' "Success Motive Study" questionnaire, Morozuk's "Sanogenic Thinking" questionnaire, "Social Opinion" questionnaire and we used questionnaires such as "Q-sorting, i.e. determining personality behavior" developed by Stefanson. In the light of our research on sanogenic thinking in early adolescents, we looked at the overall indicators of students' sanogenic thinking, taking into account the regularities and characteristics between the psychological characteristics of sanogenic thinking. Their cross-poll correlations are presented below.

Correlation values between questionnaires of personality characteristics of the respondents and Q-sort structure indicators are presented in the next table.

The results obtained from the research on the psychological characteristics of sanogenic thinking in early adolescents show that the correlation between the factors on the questionnaires for the study of opportunities between the level of personality characteristics of respondents studying in public educational institutions and the indicators of Q-sort questionnaires are more dependent factors: independent ($r=0.373$, $r \leq 0,05$) with factors, independent scale: personality ($r=0,320$, $r \leq 0,05$) with factors, input scale: anxiety ($r=0,329$,

$r \leq 0,05$) and success motive ($r=0,500, r \leq 0,01$) with the factors of the personality scale: anxiety ($r=0,335, r \leq 0,05$) and sanogenic thinking ($r=0,388, r \leq 0,05$) with the factors of the fighter scale: avoiding the fight ($r=0,539, r \leq 0,01$) and sanogenic thinking ($r=0,377, r \leq 0,05$) with the factors of the avoidant struggle scale: achievement motive ($r=0,343, r \leq 0,01$) with the anxiety scale: achievement motive ($r=0,905, r \leq 0,01$), with factors of sanogenic thinking ($r=0,709, r \leq 0,01$) and social opinion ($r=0,636, r \leq 0,01$), success motive scale: level of sanogenic thinking ($r=0,689, r \leq 0,01$) and social opinion level ($r=0,606, r \leq 0,01$) factors, to see that there is a moderate correlation between factors such as Sanogenic thinking scale: social opinion ($r=0,923, r \leq 0,01$) possible The next table shows the correlations of early adolescents' personality characteristics and Q-sort questionnaires.

The results of questionnaires on the level of anxiety, success motive, social thinking, social opinion, and Q-sorting that serve to develop sanogenic thinking in early adolescents showed that the correlational relationships between the personality characteristics of the respondents selected from the Bekobod district and the personality behavior questionnaires were interrelated factors. more dependent scale: with factors of enterprising ($r=0,328, r \leq 0,05$) and struggling ($r=0,370, r \leq 0,05$), independent scale: with factors of achievement motive ($r=0,349, r \leq 0,05$), inclusive scale: struggling ($r=0,353, r \leq 0,05$), anxiety ($r=0,316, r \leq 0,05$), sanogenic thinking ($r=0,341, r \leq 0,05$) and social thinking ($r=0,364, r \leq 0,05$) with the factors Adamovi scale: struggle avoider ($r=0,381, r \leq 0,05$) and anxiety ($r=0,385, r \leq 0,05$) factors, the fighter scale: success motive ($r=0,339, r \leq 0,05$) and sanogenic thinking ($r=0,343, r \leq 0,05$) with the factors of the struggle avoider scale: social thought ($r=0,366, r \leq 0,05$) with the factors of the anxiety scale: achievement motive ($r=0,779, r \leq 0,01$), with the factors of sanogenic thinking ($r=0,772, r \leq 0,01$) and social opinion ($r=0,675, r \leq 0,01$), the achievement motive scale: sanogenic thinking ($r=0,778, r \leq 0,01$) and with factors of social opinion ($r=0,771, r \leq 0,01$), to see that the sanogenic thinking scale: social opinion ($r=0,960, r \leq 0,01$) was highly correlated possible The following table shows the level of personal characteristics of the respondents selected from the Tashkent city school and their correlations according to the Q-sorting questionnaires.

The results of the study on the socio-psychological characteristics of the development of sanogenic thinking in early adolescents show that the correlation between the factors of the questionnaires for the study of opportunities between the level of personality characteristics and indicators of personality behavior is more dependent factors: independent ($r=0,324, r \leq 0,05$) and with the factors of struggle-avoidance ($r=0,389, r \leq 0,05$), independent scale: struggle ($r=0,318, r \leq 0,05$) with factors, input scale: struggle-avoidance ($r=0,369, r \leq 0,05$) and achievement motive ($r=0,360, r \leq 0,05$) factors, with the personality scale: struggle avoider ($r=0,345, r \leq 0,05$) factors, the fighter scale: anxiety ($r=0,406, r \leq 0,05$) and success motive ($r=0,378, r \leq 0,05$) with the factors of the avoidant struggle scale: anxiety ($r=0,321, r \leq 0,05$) with the factors of the anxiety scale: success motive ($r=0,818, r \leq 0,01$), with the factors of sanogenic thinking ($r=0,699, r \leq 0,01$) and social opinion ($r=0,695, r \leq 0,01$), success motive scale: sanogenic thinking ($r=0,767, r \leq 0,01$) and with factors of social opinion ($r=0,716, r \leq 0,01$), it can be seen that there is a high degree of correlation between factors such as sanogenic thinking scale: social opinion ($r=0,936, r \leq 0,01$). The next section presents structural models of early adolescent personality and Q-sort questionnaires.

In order to strengthen the practical aspects of the scientific research conducted on the

socio-psychological features of the development of sanogen thinking, the questionnaires conducted in early adolescents provided an opportunity to determine the higher or lower scales according to the structural model. According to the region, the respondents selected from the schools of Karshi city formed the higher structural units reflected in the questionnaires: units such as success motive, sanogenic thinking, subordination, enterprising and sociable, and the lower scales: psychological structural units such as anxiety, social opinion, independent, combative and avoidant. , the respondents selected from the schools of Bekobod district have high psychological units: anxiety, dependence, enterprising, fighting and avoiding fighting units, and the lower level psychological characteristics such as success motive, sanogenic thinking, social thinking, independent and sociable, selected from general secondary schools of Tashkent city it can be seen that high psychological units in the obtained respondents: anxiety, achievement motive, dependent, independent and humanistic scales, and the higher result reflects psychological structural models such as synogenic thinking, social thinking, enterprising, fighting and avoiding fighting.

In our next report, the inter-reliability levels of the questionnaires used in the study are reflected according to the Cronbach's Alpha criterion. (See Table 4.7).

Table 4.7

Indices of validity between personality questionnaires

Validity of questionnaires Alpha Cronbach

(0.25-1)

Spielberger Haney's Anxiety Test 0.44%

Ehlers' Achievement Motivation Questionnaire 0.83%

Morozyuk's "Sanogenic Thinking" methodology 0.96%

Survey "Social opinion" 0.80%

Stefanson questionnaire 0.26%

Cronbach's Alpha criterion was used to determine the appropriateness of the questionnaires used in the scientific-practical research on the socio-psychological characteristics of the development of sanogenic thinking in the respondents. According to this statistical criterion, the questionnaire used to measure the level of anxiety showed moderate reliability and validity. The second achievement motivation questionnaire showed a high level in examining the motivational domain of the subjects. The main psychological aspect of this is that early adolescents can be determined by the fact that they understood the content of this questionnaire, performed it consistently, or had a convenient time and good conditions. The results of the test subjects also showed the highest level according to the Sanogen thinking questionnaire. The validity level of the survey designed to determine social opinion was also high. We can see that the results of the test subjects on the last questionnaire Q-sort questionnaire were below average.

According to the results of the scientific research on the socio-psychological characteristics of the development of sanogenic thinking in the respondents, it was determined that the inter-correlation relations of the test-takers on the used questionnaires formed a medium level of psychological dependence, and the levels of mutual reliability of the tests and questionnaires that serve to develop the sanogenic thinking in the respondents were also consistently reliable.

Educating young people to be intellectually rich, free-thinking, strong knowledge holders is in line with the centuries-old dreams and hopes of our ancestors, and the implementation of these tasks in all aspects of the educational process is a socio-psychological problem.

It is necessary to carry out educational activities in cooperation with educational institutions, family, community, and the general public. To do this, it is necessary to expand the scope of spiritual and educational views of young people, to abandon polished methods and to develop a new, systematic methodology and pedagogical training that meets the requirements of the time. "Youth Union" social movement, "Women's Committees, "Neighborhood Activists", authorities on religious enlightenment, spirituality and moral education in the neighborhoods should actively participate in the educational activities carried out on the basis of a systematic plan.

It should cover all aspects of the level of development of sanogenic thinking in young people (physical, mental, spiritual, educational level) and serve to continuously improve their skills.

The development of sanogenic thinking in young people is carried out in the following order: a model of social-psychological mechanisms of behavior is developed; the diagnostic object is selected; diagnostic methodology is determined (developed); Health care activities aimed at developing sanogenic thinking are carried out.

Research has confirmed that the development of sanogenic thinking in young people is positive in the following cases:

To ensure the intellectual growth of young learners by expanding their emotional world; achieve elimination of behavioral defects through their intellectual growth; it is necessary to use complex assignments aimed at improving moral qualities.

References:

1. Tursunovna, A. K. (2024). A THEORETICAL APPROACH TO THE INTERPRETATION OF LEXICAL UNITS OF TRANSLATOR, A GUIDE-TRANSLATOR AND A TOUR GUIDE. *Western European Journal of Linguistics and Education*, 2(4), 209-214.
2. Алимова, К. (2020). Feature of the guide-translator's rhetoric. in *Library*, 20(4), 242-245.
3. Алимова, К. (2024). Features of the speech of male and female translation guides. *Зарубежная лингвистика и лингводидактика*, 2(2), 85-90.
4. Алимова, К. (2021). Гид-таржимон нутқида риториканинг ахамияти. in *Library*, 21(4), 39-42.
5. Tolkinovich, U. J. (2023). Hazrati Imom (Hastimom) Me'moriy Majmuasinig Qayta Tiklanishi.
6. Tolkinovich, U. J. (2023). ARCHITECTURAL PRINCIPLES OF SHRINES IN UZBEKISTAN. *Open Access Repository*, 4(3), 1060-1064.
7. Tolkinovich, U. J. (2023). THE LEVEL OF SEISMIC RESISTANCE OF RESIDENTIAL BUILDINGS IN ARCHITECTURE. *Open Access Repository*, 4(03), 141-147.
8. Tolkinovich, U. J. (2023). MONUMENTS INCLUDED IN THE UNESCO LIST IN HISTORICAL CITIES OF UZBEKISTAN. *Open Access Repository*, 4(3), 1048-1053.
9. Tolkinovich, U. J. (2023). REPAIR AND RESTORATION OF ARCHITECTURAL MONUMENTS. *Open Access Repository*, 4(3), 1054-1059.
10. Tolqinovich, O. J. (2022). Modern Residential Buildings in the Historical Part of

Samarkand Formation of Modern Typology. European Journal of Life Safety and Stability (2660-9630), 13, 87-92.

11. O'Sarov, J. T. L. (2022). TURARJOY BINOLARINI QAYTA TIKLASH VA SHAKLLANTIRISH MUAMMOLARI. Scientific progress, 3(2), 96-101.

12. Tolqinovich, O. J. (2022). Architecture of Traditional Residential Buildings in Historical Cities of Uzbekistan. EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF BUSINESS STARTUPS AND OPEN SOCIETY, 2(1), 65-69.

13. Tolqinovich, O. J. (2022). IT Has Not Been Saved to US in Bukhara" Madrasah's Cure". EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF BUSINESS STARTUPS AND OPEN SOCIETY, 2(2), 9-13.

14. Qazaqovna, K. M. (2024). HEUTAGOGY: UNLEASHING LEARNER AUTONOMY AND SELF-DIRECTED LEARNING: AN IN-DEPTH EXPLORATION. Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal, 12(1), 302-305.

15. Xidirova, M., & Abdurahobov, S. (2023). THE ROLE OF PHYSICAL CULTURE IN THE FORMATION OF PERSONAL CHARACTERISTICS. Modern Science and Research, 2(12), 397-400.

16. Ergasheva, S. A. (2021). History of baisun silk knitting factory. ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal, 11(5), 581-585.

17. Ergasheva, S. A. (2020). CRAFT OF SURKHANOAKH FROM THE HISTORY OF DEVELOPMENT. Theoretical & Applied Science, (7), 56-59.

18. Ergasheva, S. A. (2020). The history of surkhan doppies (skullcups) and the characteristics of this folk craft. American Journal of Social and Humanitarian Research, 1(6), 7-13.

19. Abdusolatovna, E. S. (2023). SURXONDARYO VILOYATI IQTISODIY RIVOJLANISHIDA BOYSUN AN'ANAVIY HUNARMANDCHILIGINING O'RNI. PEDAGOGS jurnali, 31(1), 10-17.

20. Abdusolatovna, E. S. (2023). The Role of Crafts in the Economy of Surkhan Oakh (In the Example of Cosibility).

INNOVATIVE
ACADEMY